

APPLICATION OF BIBLIOMETRIC LAWS IN GLOBAL LIMNOLOGY RESEARCH PUBLICATIONS: A SCIENTOMETRIC ANALYSIS BASED ON WEB OF SCIENCE 1989-2020

S. GUNASEELAN

Research Scholar
Department of Library and Information Science
Bharathidasan University
Tiruchirappalli-620024
Tamil Nadu, India
E-mail: gunaseelan2703@gmail.com

Dr. C. RANGANATHAN

Associate Professor
Department of Library and Information Science
Bharathidasan University
Tiruchirappalli-620024
Tamil Nadu, India
E-mail: cranganathan72@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This paper deals with the application of various bibliometric laws in global limnology research publications based on Web of Science during 1989-2020. A total of 1499 papers were found from 402 journals. It is found that the mean growth rate is 0.16 and doubling time 7.74 years, the journal 'Hydrobiologia' ranked the top, findings does not fit Bradford's law, John P. Simol is the prolific author in Limnology, the analysis invalidates Lotka's law, Lake and Lakes are the important key words, the findings fit in Zipf's law. In addition, the author's applied Price's square root law and Pareto Principle. This study provides the dynamics of research activity and help in gauging the field of Limnology. Further useful to scientists and information professionals in the field.

Keywords: *Scientometrics, Bibliometrics, Informetrics, Bibliometric Analysis, Research Trends, Relative Growth Rate, Lotka's Law, Bradford's Law, Zipf's Law, Pareto Principle, Price's Law, Limnology, Lakes, Rivers, Pond, Fresh Water Oceanography.*

1. Introduction

Limnology is the study of waters found within continents. Oxford English Language dictionary defines 'limnology as the study of the biological, chemical and physical features of lakes and other bodies of fresh water'. The word limnology comes from the Greek word limne, meaning 'lake or pond' and logos meaning 'the study of'. Thus, limnology covers all inland waters (lakes, streams, rivers, ground water, wet lands etc.). Limnologists can otherwise be called as 'fresh water oceanography' also. But it also covers reservoirs, inland salt and brackish water or slightly salt water. All these offer enormous benefits to human society, environmental well-being and economic welfare.

Bibliometric or scientometric methods were used to measure the scientific development of disciplines. Scientometrics is now part of sociology of science and is beneficial in science policy formulation. Thus, this study is of great help in understanding the complete worldwide development of the subject 'limnology' and is useful to limnologists, allied scientists as well as the information professionals involved in this area. Numerous studies are seen in literature explaining the different aspects of limnology, but a bibliometric study on the growth and application of various bibliometric laws in this discipline during the period (1989-2020) has not been conducted so far, thus the necessity of this study.

2. Review of Literature

Since this paper deals with bibliometrics of limnology literature, multiple search in various databases has been done with keywords bibliometrics and scientometrics in combination with synonymous terms such as lakes, rivers, ponds, fresh water etc. Several papers were retrieved and few of the recent ones relevant to this topic are reviewed here.

The paper by Pan et al. (2023) provides a quantitative and qualitative analysis of research trends in Yangtze river basin. The study by Wen et al. (2023) provides a bibliometric analysis of river health based on publication in the last three decades. A bibliometric analysis of the yellow river basin in China has been studied by He et al. (2022). The paper by Herrera-Franco et al. (2022) aims to analyze the scientific production that deals with the study of ground water Life Cycle Assessment using bibliometric methods.

Lercari (2021) analysed data on marine science articles in Uruguay from 1990 to 2018 using Scopus database. Bibliometric analysis of research trends in aquatic microbial community recorded in Web of Science during 1991-2018 was studied by Liu et al. (2020). Ho and Goethals (2020) did a bibliometric analysis on lakes and reservoirs. Bibliometrics on literature of Poyang lake has been studied by Zhou (2019). Husain et al. (2018) did a bibliometric analysis of the published research articles on river Ganga for a period of 25 years using Science Citation Index Expanded.

Phytoplankton studies between 1991 and 2013 based on Web of Science has been done by Wang et al. (2015). Global scientific productivity of the subject 'limnology' from 2001 to 2010 based on SCI was conducted by Cao et al. (2012). This research showed that limnology research increased over the past decade. The study done by Salmaso and Mosello (2010) is based on 230 papers published during the last 15 years in International journals, aims at evaluating the state-of-the art of limnological research.

Even though not related to limnology, two bibliometric studies worth mentioning are by Rahaman and Joshi (2022) and Yadav and Meera (2022), published in this journal.

3. Objectives of the Study

Objectives of the study are:

- a) To find out the global growth of limnology publications from 1989 to 2020.
- b) To know the journals which publishes limnology research and to find out the various citation scores.
- c) To investigate the applicability of Bradford's law in limnology literature.
- d) To examine the applicability of Lotka's Law of Scientific Author Productivity in limnology literature.
- e) To analyze key word distribution and to test and validate Zipf's law of word frequency.
- f) To test Price's square root law and Pareto principle (80 x 20 rule) in limnology publications.

4. Methodology

The data for the study was gathered from "Web of Science" database from 1989 to 2020 by using the string word "Limnology" in the topic field. A total of 1499 publications were retrieved. The data was downloaded as plain text format and extracted using HistCite software. Further analysis was carried out in MS-Excel, and VoS viewer software for tabulation and mapping visualization.

4.1. Metric and Empirical Laws of Bibliometrics

4.1.1. Relative Growth Rate

The relative growth rate is the increase in the number of publications per unit of time. The mean relative growth rate R (1-2) over a specified period of interval can be calculated from the following equation

$$\bar{R} (1-2) = \frac{w_2 - w_1}{T_2 - T_1}$$

$\bar{R} (1-2)$ = Mean relative growth rate over the specified period interval

W_1 = $\log w_1$ (Natural log of initial number of publications)

W_2 = $\log w_2$ (Natural log of initial number of publications)

$T_2 - T_1$ = the unit difference between the initial time and final time

The relative growth rate for publications can be calculated separately.

Therefore \bar{R} = relative growth rate per unit publication per unit of time (year).

4.1.2. Bradford's Law

The law is mathematically expressed as

$$F_{(x)} = a + b \log X$$

Where,

$F_{(x)}$ is the cumulative number of references contained in first 'X' most productive journals.

A and B are constants.

4.1.3. Lotka's Law of Author's Productivity

Lotka's law is one of the three major laws of bibliometrics that mainly explain the distribution of literature of various author's productivity in a given field. Lotka's Law of author productivity is tested with the application of scientific productivity Chi-square model, and it is applied in relation to number of authors contributing to the number of publications. The model is applied in the present study.

The sum was used as deviser for $1/n$ 4.65 to determine the proportion of the total number of authors expected to produce 'n' paper (in the case of present study $n = 1, 2, 3...10$), the following formula was used to find the proportions.

$$S = \sum_{n=1}^{10} 1/n \ 4.65$$

For the present study S is the sum of Lotka's modified ratios for the value $a = 4.65$

The formula $a_n = 1/n \ 4.65 \ T/S$ ($n = 1, 2, 3... 10$)

Where,

T is total number of authors in the sampling

An is the total number of expected authors producing 'n' papers.

The chi - square can be computed as $(F - p)^2/p$

F = observed number of authors with 'n' publications;

P = expected number of authors.

4.1.4. Lotka's Inverse Square Law of Scientific Author Productivity

The general formula is $XY = C$

Where,

X is the number of publications

Y is the relative frequency of authors with X publications

C is constant, depending on the specific field.

The formula is also called the Inverse Square Law

The 'n' value is calculated by this method using the following formula

$$N = \frac{N \sum xy - \sum x \sum y}{N \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2}$$

Where,

N = Number of pairs of data

X = Logarithm of articles (x)

Y = Logarithm of authors (y)

4.1.5. Zipf's Law

Zipf's law is often used to predict word frequencies in full text. The law states that if you (in a relatively large text corpus): "...list the words occurring within that text in order of decreasing frequency, the rank of a word on that list multiplied by its frequency will equal a constant."

$$\text{Zipf's law: } r \times f = c$$

Where,

r = rank (in terms of frequency)

f = frequency (no. of times the given word is used in the text)

c = constant for the given text

For a given text the rank of a word multiplied by the frequency is a constant.

4.1.6. Price's Square Root Law

Price's Square Root Law which states that half (50%) of the literature on a subject will be contributed by the square root of total number of authors publishing in that area.

In order to validate whether the distribution status of authors fulfill Price's Square Root Law, the following calculation is carried out $PSQ = \sqrt{N}$.

4.1.7. Pareto Principle (80 X 20 Rule)

Pareto Principle (80 X 20 Rule) states that,

for many events, roughly 80% of the effects come from 20% of the causes. The original observation was in connection with income and wealth. Pareto noticed that 80% of Italy's wealth owned by 20% of the population. He then carried out surveys on a variety of other countries and found to his surprise that a similar distribution applied. This is applied in bibliometrics also.

5. Analysis of Data

5.1. Relative Growth Rate and Doubling Time in Limnology Research Output

Table-1 presents data of relative growth rate and doubling time for total research output in limnology. It could be noted that in 1989, 11 papers have been published in limnology and the number went up to 1499 by the end of the year 2020. The mean relative growth rates for the periods 1989-2004 and 2005-2020 are 0.25 and 0.07 respectively. The whole study period records the mean relative growth rate as 0.16. The mean doubling time for publications is 7.74 years. The mean doubling time for the period 1989 to 2004 is worked out as 4.53 and for the period 2005 to 2020 it is calculated as 10.74 years. This has been highlighted by doubling time for publications which is more than relative growth rate.

Table 1
Relative Growth Rate and Doubling Time in Limnology Research

Publica- tion Year	No. of Output	Cum. No. of Output	Log _e 1	Log _e 2	- R (a)	Mean R (a)	Dt = 0.693	Mean Dt (a)
							- R (a)	
1989	11	11	-	2.40	-	0.25	-	4.53
1990	15	26	2.40	3.26	0.86		0.81	
1991	28	54	3.26	3.99	0.73		0.95	
1992	27	81	3.99	4.39	0.40		1.71	
1993	26	107	4.39	4.67	0.28		2.45	
1994	35	142	4.67	4.96	0.29		2.42	
1995	32	174	4.96	5.16	0.20		3.48	
1996	27	201	5.16	5.30	0.14		4.84	
1997	34	235	5.30	5.46	0.16		4.34	
1998	39	274	5.46	5.61	0.15		4.53	
1999	31	305	5.61	5.72	0.11		6.28	
2000	31	336	5.72	5.82	0.10		7.14	
2001	44	380	5.82	5.94	0.12		5.77	
2002	29	409	5.94	6.01	0.07		9.40	
2003	43	452	6.01	6.11	0.10	6.68		
2004	44	496	6.11	6.21	0.10	7.18		
2005	46	542	6.21	6.30	0.09	8.13	10.74	
2006	53	595	6.30	6.39	0.09	7.83		
2007	60	655	6.39	6.48	0.09	7.32		
2008	66	721	6.48	6.58	0.10	6.89		
2009	62	783	6.58	6.66	0.08	8.34		
2010	50	833	6.66	6.73	0.07	10.66		
2011	53	886	6.73	6.79	0.06	12.22		
2012	54	940	6.79	6.85	0.06	12.40		
2013	51	991	6.85	6.90	0.05	14.23		
2014	77	1068	6.90	6.97	0.07	9.42		
2015	58	1126	6.97	7.03	0.06	12.28		
2016	70	1196	7.03	7.09	0.06	12.21		
2017	67	1263	7.09	7.14	0.05	13.52		
2018	65	1328	7.14	7.19	0.05	13.47		
2019	78	1406	7.19	7.25	0.06	11.85		
2020	93	1499	7.25	7.31	0.06	11.08		
Mean					0.16	0.16	7.74	7.74

5.2. Analysis the Ranked List of Journals and Articles

It is seen from the analysis (table 2) that the total research output of limnology from 1989 to 2020 was published in 402 journals. The first 25 journals cover majority of the research productivity (43.9%), which corresponds to the theory of Bradford's Law of journal scattering in research productivity. These top twenty-five journals accounted for 43.9% of research output. The journal "*Hydrobiologia*" ranked first with 146

publications and a Global Citation Score of 3884. *Hydrobiologia* is an international journal of aquatic science (peer-reviewed) publishes original research investigating the biology of freshwater and marine habitats. This is followed by "*Journal of Paleolimnology*" has 41 publications with the Global Citation Score of 1641. Next in order is the journal "*Limnology and Oceanography*" with 39 publications with the Global Citation Score of 2228 respectively.

Table 2
Ranked List of Journals and Articles

Journal	Article	%	TLCS	TLCS/ t	TGCS	TGCS/ t	TLCR
Hydrobiologia	146	9.7	404	20.86	3884	235.79	187
Journal of Paleolimnology	41	2.7	78	4.85	1641	103.7	72
Limnology and Oceanography	39	2.6	41	2.57	2228	164.65	40
Journal of Great Lakes Research	36	2.4	55	4.85	639	69.95	41
International Review of Hydrobiology	34	2.3	174	9.21	1024	65.82	92
Journal of Limnology	32	2.1	21	2.94	344	47.35	87
Revista De Biologia Tropical	29	1.9	22	1.17	261	18.33	15
Freshwater Biology	28	1.9	36	3.68	648	55.48	64
Science of the Total Environment	25	1.7	14	1.74	651	71.2	56
Aquatic Sciences	24	1.6	35	2.83	723	59.59	58
Archiv Fur Hydrobiologie	23	1.5	95	4.09	304	13.18	49
Brazilian Journal of Biology	20	1.3	12	1.18	394	36.69	9
Inland Waters	20	1.3	17	2.83	192	47.98	41
Ecological Modelling	18	1.2	12	1.11	379	40.15	16
Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences	17	1.1	170	7.63	813	45.55	45
Limnologica	17	1.1	21	1.31	174	20.09	12
Internationale Revue Der Gesamten Hydrobiologie	14	0.9	7	0.26	80	2.92	1
Arctic Antarctic And Alpine Research	13	0.9	45	2.59	370	21.83	66

Environmental Monitoring and Assessment	13	0.9	2	0.24	132	17.34	9
Lake and Reservoir Management	13	0.9	26	1.46	229	14.6	27
Limnetica	13	0.9	8	0.77	329	32.02	5
Aquatic Ecology	12	0.8	18	1.39	245	22.99	15
Limnology	12	0.8	4	0.35	89	9.07	4
Antarctic Science	11	0.7	36	2.14	344	21.15	18
Bangladesh Journal of Botany	11	0.7	7	0.51	23	1.42	7
Total	661	43.9	1360	82.56	16140	1238.84	1036
<p>TLCS = Total Local Citation Score TLGCS = Total Global Citation Score TLCR = Total Local Cited Reference TLCS/t = Total Local Citation Score per Year TLGCS/t = Total Global Citation Score per Year</p>							

Fig. 1: Network Visualization of Citation of Source Journals

5.3. Application of Bradford's Law

It is found (table-3) that eighteen journals covered more than one third of the total articles published. The next 60 journals covered another one third of the articles. The remaining 278 journals covered the last one

third of the published articles. According to Bradford's distribution, the relationship between the zone is $1: a: a^2$, while the relationship between each zone of the present study is 18:60:278. Thus it does not fit into Bradford's distribution.

Table 3
Ranking of Journals according to Bradford's Law

SI. No.	No. of Journals	No. of Contribution	Total Number of Contribution	Cumulative Total
1	1	13	13	13
2	1	15	15	28
3	1	18	18	46
4	1	20	20	66
5	1	21	21	87
6	1	23	23	110
7	1	25	25	135
8	1	28	28	163
9	1	37	37	200
10	1	103	103	303
11	2	11	22	325
12	2	16	32	357
13	2	17	34	391
14	2 (18)	22	44	435 (2659)
15	3	12	36	471
16	4	8	32	503
17	5	7	35	538
18	5	10	50	588
19	7	6	42	630
20	8	5	40	670
21	9	9	81	751
22	19 (60)	4	76	827 (4978)
23	41	3	123	950
24	54	2	108	1058
25	183 (278)	1	183	1241 (3249)

5.4. Bradford's Distribution of Journals in Various Zones

Bradford's law of verbal formulation was calculated with the multiplier by dividing the number of journals in a zone by preceding zone's number of journals. The publications

were divided in to three zones. Hence, 402 journals represent the nucleus zone and the mean value of multiplier is 3.99. Therefore $1*18: 3.99*18: (3.99)^2*18 = 153.34$ which does not fit to the Bradford's law of scattering for the present study.

Table 4
Bradford's Distribution in Various Zones

Zone	No. of Journals	No. of Publications	Multiplier Factor
1	18	2659	-
2	60	4978	3.33
3	278	3249	4.63
Total	356	10886	3.99

5.5. Author Productivity

The author data of limnology research revealed that there were 4537 authors contributed 1499 publications. As shown in Table-5, on the basis of number of publications, the most prolific author is Smol, J.P. who topped the list with total 64 publications. John P. Smol is a professor in

the Department of Biology of Queens University, Ontario, Canada. This is followed by Douglas, MSV with 32 publications. Marianne S.V. Douglas is affiliated with University of Alberta, Canada, However, the result would be quite different, if the listing done by Total Global Citation received by authors. Smol, J P., has 2742 citations followed by Douglas, M S V., has 1614 citations.

Table 5
Ranking of Prolific Authors based on publications

Author	No. of Papers	%	TLCS	TGCS	TLCR	TLCSb	TLCSe
Smol J P	64	4.3	727	2742	422	155	35
Douglas M S V	32	2.1	474	1614	285	118	26
Pienitz R	18	1.2	225	837	75	26	10
Vincent W F	14	0.9	49	627	26	8	
Antoniades D	12	0.8	94	307	110	33	5
Blais J M	12	0.8	18	262	56	1	
Hall R I	12	0.8	26	588	52	8	0
Michelutti N	11	0.7	111	321	110	36	3
Hutter K	10	0.7	16	135	16	12	0
Khondker M	10	0.7	7	23	7	2	
Verschuren D	10	0.7	18	454	23	3	3
Vyverman W	10	0.7	26	219	32	7	0
Wolfe B B	10	0.7	18	232	49	8	
Gajewski K	9	0.6	80	285	70	11	8

Hecky R E	9	0.6	61	618	20	8	1
Lean D R S	9	0.6	314	554	49	60	18
Verleyen E	9	0.6	20	197	34	6	1
Hansson L A	8	0.5	5	722	2	0	1
Hodgson D A	8	0.5	28	249	21	6	4
Jones J R	8	0.5	22	212	24	5	2
McGowan S	8	0.5	14	265	27	6	0
Rautio M	8	0.5	34	280	25	3	1
Twiss M R	8	0.5	42	348	15	6	4
Wagner B	8	0.5	14	280	18	6	0
Anderson N J	7	0.5	12	181	29	2	0
Total	324	21.6	2455	12552	1597	536	122
TLCS = Total Local Citation Score TLGCS = Total Global Citation Score TLCR = Total Local Cited Reference TLCSb = Total Local Citation Score in the beginning TLCSe = Total Local Citation Score in the end							

5.6. Lotka's Law of Author Productivity – Inverse Square Model

Analysis given in table-5 indicates the application of Lotka's law with respect to author productivity of limnology research. It could be seen clearly from the table that the

proportion of all contribution that makes a single contribution is 10%. It means that the collaborative author's contribution is very high. So, the fact that the tabulated values show that observed author's value is more than expected value. Thus, the present analysis clearly invalidates Lotka's findings.

Table 6
Lotka's Law of Author Productivity – Inverse Square Model

No. of Contribution (x)	No. of Contributor/ author (y)	x*y	$\sum X = \log_e x$	$\sum Y = \log_e y$	$\sum X * \sum Y$	$\sum X * \sum X$
1	3695	3695	0.00	8.21	0.00	0.00
2	542	1084	0.69	6.99	4.84	0.48
3	140	420	1.10	6.04	6.64	1.21
4	73	292	1.39	5.68	7.87	1.92
5	37	185	1.61	5.22	8.40	2.59
6	20	120	1.79	4.79	8.58	3.21
7	6	42	1.95	3.74	7.27	3.79
8	7	56	2.08	4.03	8.37	4.32
9	4	36	2.20	3.58	7.87	4.83
10	5	50	2.30	3.91	9.01	5.30
11	1	11	2.40	2.40	5.75	5.75
12	3	36	2.48	3.58	8.90	6.17
14	1	14	2.64	2.64	6.96	6.96
18	1	18	2.89	2.89	8.35	8.35
32	1	32	3.47	3.47	12.01	12.01
64	1	64	4.16	4.16	17.30	17.30
Total	4537	6155	33.14	8.73	128.14	84.20

5.7. Lotka's Law of Author Productivity- Chi-Square Model

The Lotka's law of author productivity is tested using the scientific productivity Chi-Square model and it is applied in relation to the number of authors who contribute to the number of publications. It is important to consider the implications of Lotka's law in terms of author productivity in limnology. It explains that the proportion of authors who make "n" contributors who make a single

contribution is approximately 60%. The productivity of limnology scientists is investigated in this study. The analysed data, at first glance, invalidate Lotka's findings that the proportion of all contributions that make a single contribution is less than 60%.

Further, Lotka's Chi-Square model confirms the source trend. It explains that the calculated x^2 value is 13011.11 which is greater than table value at 5 percent level of significance is not proved (the implication of Lotka's law related with author productivity in limnology).

Table 7
Lotka's Law of Author Productivity- Chi- Square Model

No. of Contributions	Observed Number of authors with "n" or (an) or (f)	Observed percentage of authors 100 x an/al	Expected number of authors (an=a1/n ²) or (p)	Expected percentage of authors	(F-P) ² /p
1	222	100	222	100	0.00
2	288	129.73	55.5	25	973.99
3	292	131.53	24.67	11.11	2897.32
4	252	113.51	13.88	6.25	4086.74
5	142	63.96	8.88	4.00	1995.60
6	103	46.40	6.17	2.78	1520.55
7	52	23.42	4.53	2.04	497.36
8	36	16.22	3.47	1.56	305.09
9	27	12.16	2.74	1.23	214.73
10	20	9.01	2.22	1.00	142.40
11	15	6.76	1.83	0.83	94.47
12	18	8.11	1.54	0.69	175.70
13	6	2.70	1.31	0.59	16.72
14	4	1.80	1.13	0.51	7.26
15	6	2.70	0.99	0.44	25.47
16	1	0.45	0.87	0.39	0.02
17	3	1.35	0.77	0.35	6.48
18	1	0.45	0.69	0.31	0.14
19	2	0.90	0.61	0.28	3.12
20	2	0.90	0.56	0.25	3.76
23	1	0.45	0.42	0.19	0.80
24	1	0.45	0.39	0.17	0.98
34	1	0.45	0.19	0.09	3.40
42	1	0.45	0.13	0.06	6.07
44	1	0.45	0.11	0.05	6.84
53	1	0.45	0.08	0.04	10.73
62	1	0.45	0.06	0.03	15.37
				x²	13011.11

5.8. Most Used Keywords in Limnology

Table-8 lists the top 25 keywords associated with the subject limnology. The important words known as “key words” are one of the best indicators for understanding and grasping the thought content of the papers, methodologies used and areas of research addressed in an instant. The highest frequently used keywords are “Lake” which has 435 records and rank first and the Global

Citation Score is 8672. The next most used word is “Lakes” which has 316 records and ranks second in frequency and has a Global Citation Score of 9586. Next most used word is “Limnology” which has 302 records and ranks third in frequency and has a Global Citation Score of 5148. According to these TLSC, TGCS analyses the “Lakes” have the highest Global Citation Score of 9586 followed by the “Lake” which has the second highest Global Citation Score of 8672.

Table 8
Most Used Keywords in Limnology Research

Sl. No.	Word	Records	%	TLCS	TGCS
1	Lake	435	29	546	8672
2	Lakes	316	21.1	977	9586
3	Limnology	302	20.1	793	5148
4	Water	167	11.1	84	2221
5	Limnological	99	6.6	283	2092
6	Arctic	94	6.3	727	3565
7	Reservoir	93	6.2	44	932
8	High	92	6.1	465	2483
9	Phytoplankton	81	5.4	62	1732
10	Tropical	79	5.3	67	1683
11	Environmental	72	4.8	126	2659
12	River	72	4.8	53	1249
13	Freshwater	70	4.7	97	3361
14	Canada	65	4.3	416	2029
15	Chemical	64	4.3	428	1381
16	Aquatic	62	4.1	44	1757
17	Quality	60	4	13	951
18	Climate	56	3.7	110	2488
19	Dynamics	55	3.7	51	731
20	Physical	53	3.5	460	1504
21	Using	53	3.5	36	1108
22	Change	51	3.4	138	1716
23	Island	51	3.4	419	1505
24	Diatom	50	3.3	189	1708
25	Ponds	50	3.3	346	1640

Fig. 2: Overlay Visualization of Co-occurrence of Keywords

5.9. Application of Zipf’s Law

Zipf’s law states that, “in a long textual matter if words are arranged in their decreasing order of frequency, then the rank of any given word of the text will be inversely proportional to the frequency of occurrence of the word”. i.e. $r \cdot f$ (where ‘r’ is the rank and ‘f’ is the frequency.)

$$R \cdot f = C$$

(Where C is constant)

Taking log on both sides,

$$\text{Log } (f) + \text{Log } (r) = \text{Log } c$$

Or $\text{Log } (f) + \text{Log } (r) = (\text{where ‘c’ is constant})$

To apply this law, the words (terms) were collected from the title of the articles and ranked according to their frequency of occurrence in decreasing order.

Only those twenty five words occupying frequency up to 3902 items are given in table. On applying this law, it was found that log of frequency of occurrence of words when added to log of their rank; the results are almost same for each word. The log of frequency of three most potent words appeared in the titles “Lake” is given below:

Word	:	Lake
Frequency	:	435
Rank	:	1

Log of frequency + log of rank

$$\text{Log } 435 + \text{log } 1$$

$$= 2.64 + 0$$

$$= 2.64 \text{ words.}$$

Thus, it is proved that Zipf’s law is valid even today.

Table 9
Ranking of Word Occurrence in Zipf's Law

SI. No.	Word	Publication (F)	Rank (R)	Log F	Log R	Log C
1	Lake	435	1	2.64	0.00	2.64
2	Lakes	316	2	2.50	0.30	2.80
3	Limnology	302	3	2.48	0.48	2.96
4	Water	167	4	2.22	0.60	2.82
5	Limnological	99	5	2.00	0.70	2.69
6	Arctic	94	6	1.97	0.78	2.75
7	Reservoir	93	7	1.97	0.85	2.81
8	High	92	8	1.96	0.90	2.87
9	Phytoplankton	81	9	1.91	0.95	2.86
10	Tropical	79	10	1.90	1.00	2.90
11	Environmental	72	11	1.86	1.04	2.90
12	River	72	11	1.86	1.04	2.90
13	Freshwater	70	12	1.85	1.08	2.92
14	Canada	65	13	1.81	1.11	2.93
15	Chemical	64	14	1.81	1.15	2.95
16	Aquatic	62	15	1.79	1.18	2.97
17	Quality	60	16	1.78	1.20	2.98
18	Climate	56	17	1.75	1.23	2.98
19	Dynamics	55	18	1.74	1.26	3.00
20	Physical	53	19	1.72	1.28	3.00
21	Using	53	19	1.72	1.28	3.00
22	Change	51	20	1.71	1.30	3.01
23	Island	51	20	1.71	1.30	3.01
24	Diatom	50	21	1.70	1.32	3.02
25	Ponds	50	21	1.70	1.32	3.02

5.10. Application of Price's Square Root Law

In order to validate whether the distribution status of authors fulfill Price's Square Root Law and the calculation is based on;

$$PSQ = \sqrt{N} = 78.42 \quad N = 6151$$

Most (81.44%) of the authors have contributed only once in limnology publications, 11.95% of the authors have contributed two times; 3.09% of the authors

have contributed three times; 1.61% of the authors have contributed four times; 0.82% of the authors have contributed five times; 0.44% of the authors have contributed six times; 0.15% of the authors contributed seven time; 0.13% of the authors have contributed eight times; 0.11% of the authors contributed nine times; 0.09% of authors contributed ten times.

Based on the Price's Square Root Law, the only one contributor produced 64, 32, 18, 14 and 12 numbers of articles by single

contributor who have given publications; the square root value is located at just 0.52% of publications. Most of the authors have contributed very smaller number of times in Limnology research. The contribution percentage of 78.42 (Nearly root value of 6151) contributors is located at 0.52% of publications. The value is very far away from 50% (half of the literature on a subject); so this result is not in compliance Price's Square Root Law. The table below shows the related result values to be highlighted.

Table 10
Price's Square Root Law Applied in Limnology Research

No. of Contribution A	No. of contributors B	% of 4537	A*B	% of A*B	% Cumulated value of A*B	Cumulated Value of A*B
64	1	0.02	64	1.04	1.04	64
32 (96)	1	0.02 (0.04)	32 (96)	0.52 (1.56)	1.56	96
18	1	0.02	18	0.29	1.85	114
14	1	0.02	14	0.23	2.08	128
12	1	0.02	12	0.20	2.28	140
11	3	0.07	33	0.54	2.82	173
10	4	0.09	40	0.65	3.47	213
9	5	0.11	45	0.73	4.2	258
8	6	0.13	48	0.78	4.98	306
7	7	0.15	49	0.80	5.78	355
6	20	0.44	120	1.95	7.73	475
5	37	0.82	185	3.01	10.74	660
4	73	1.61	292	4.75	15.49	952
3	140	3.09	420	6.83	22.32	1372
2	542	11.95	1084	17.62	39.94	2456
1	3695	81.44	3695	60.07	100	6151
206	4537	100	6151	100	—	—

5.11. Application of Pareto Principle (80 x 20 Rule)

Pareto Principle tests whether 80% of contributions have come from 20% of contributors. Since total number of authors is 6151 which means 20% of the total number of authors is 1372. Total number of publications is 1499 and total number of

authors is 6151 and its 80% of publications value is 4779.

Based on analysis, the value of “Cumulated % A*B” is 22.32% of authors contributed more than 20% of contributions, once the “Cumulated Contributors” is 1372. In 80 X 20 rule view, 80% of author’s publications are 4779. It can be concluded that the result follows Pareto Principles.

Table 11
Application of Pareto Principle (80 x 20 Rule) in Limnology Research

No. of Contribution A	No. of contributors B	% of 4537	A*B	% of A*B	% Cumulated value of A*B	Cumulated Value of A*B
64	1	0.02	64	1.04	1.04	64
32	1	0.02	32	0.52	1.56	96
18	1	0.02	18	0.29	1.85	114
14	1	0.02	14	0.23	2.08	128
12	1	0.02	12	0.20	2.28	140
11	3	0.07	33	0.54	2.82	173
10	4	0.09	40	0.65	3.47	213
9	5	0.11	45	0.73	4.2	258
8	6	0.13	48	0.78	4.98	306
7	7	0.15	49	0.80	5.78	355
6	20	0.44	120	1.95	7.73	475
5	37	0.82	185	3.01	10.74	660
4	73	1.61	292	4.75	15.49	952
3 (203)	140 (300)	3.09	420 (1372)	6.83	22.32	1372 (22.32)
2	542	11.95	1084	17.62	39.94	2456
1	3695	81.44	3695 (4779)	60.07	100	6151 (77.69)
206	4537	100	6151	100	—	—

6. Findings

The findings of the study are as follows:

- a) World publications in limnology are increasing year by year.
- b) Mean relative growth rate is 0.16.
- c) Mean doubling time of publications is 7.74 years.
- d) Twenty-five journals in limnology has a research productivity of 43.9%.
- e) The journal '*Hydrobiologia*' publishes the maximum number of articles in limnology research with a Global Citation Score of 3884 with 146 papers.
- f) *Journal of Paleolimnology* is second in the journal rank list.
- g) Eighteen journals covered more than one third of the total articles, next 60 journals covered the other one third, and 278 journals the last one third. Thus this is not fitting in Bradford's law.
- h) Most prolific author is John P.Smol affiliated to the Queens University, Ontario, Canada. Marianno S.V.Douglas is the second most productive author in limnology.
- i) Author productivity in World limnology literature invalidates Lotka's law.
- j) Most used keyword in the discipline is 'Lake' with Global Citation Score of 8672. Next in order is 'Lakes' and the third in the list is 'Limnology'.
- k) Zipf's law is valid in limnology literature.
- l) Price's square root value is very far away from 50% (half of literature in a subject). Therefore, it does not follow Price's square root law.
- m) In 80x20 rule, 80% of the publications are 4779. Therefore, the result follows Pareto principle.

7. Conclusion

The findings of this study show that like other scientific disciplines, the number of publications in limnology are increasing annually. Thus, it is inferred that limnology scientists are working actively to increase their research articles in high impact factor journals. Top most journals in limnology identified were of great help to the researchers and information scientists. There may be several reasons why distribution of limnology articles does not conform to Bradford's law. Most prolific authors in the field identified through this study will benefit the researchers in limnology to interact with them for their research work. The reason why author productivity distribution does not conform to lotka's law is that there are many authors who contribute to limnology field with single articles only. Most used key words identified provide valuable information for those researchers who intend to search for articles in the field of limnology. It conforms to Zipf's law because the number of words that appear several times in the titles are very high. Conformity was seen in 80/20 rule also. The researcher did not study the subfields of limnology in detail. Therefore, further research is needed to conduct bibliometric analysis of publications in the subfields of limnology also to get a clear idea.

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